

Medical Waste Generation and its Management – An Analysis

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Abstract

Population growth is very high in developing countries, so the problem of poverty and unemployment is increasing day by day. To fulfill the requirement of the over population the facilities are developing in the developing countries. Medical waste management is a big challenge of the health facilities. These health facilities are developing day by day and the treatment facilities of waste are not developing in developing countries. So a huge amount of solid waste is increasing at alarming rate here. Untreated medical waste is hand overed to the municipal authority to deposition it. Such types of waste generate the environmental degradation problems and effects on the human health. Very few medical facilities have suitable management of it but mostly medical facilities have not proper management of medical waste. Plastics, papers, polythene, metals, cardboard, trees leaf, waste foods, human tissues, glass, cloths etc. are found in medical waste. Hospitals, nursing home, clinics and pathology labs are the main sources of solid waste generation of the health facilities. Due to poor management of solid waste of the medical facilities the problem of environmental degradation is increasing at alarming rate here. Hazardous waste is very dangerous to the human health. It is estimated that it is almost 15% of the total amount of the medical waste. Such types of waste contains potentially harmful micro organism that can be spread among healthcare personnel, hospitals, patients and the general public, causing serious illness.

Keywords Health Facilities, Medical Waste, Solid Waste, Environmental Degradation, Health Issues, Poor Management.

Introduction

Medical facilities are essential to control the diseases and controlled the death rate. Medical facilities are a big generator of the solid waste in urban areas. So untreated medical waste is deposited here because these facilities have poor management of it. Everybody knows that medical waste is very harmful to the environment and the human health, because different types of chemicals are used to investigate the diseases by the pathology labs. According to the annual report on biomedical waste management 2022 the biomedical waste was generated about 705 tonnes per day in India. It was treated 645 tonnes by the related authorities. Bio-medical waste generation depends on the number of the healthcare facilities, types of healthcare facilities and the population density. At present we noticed a big gap between medical waste generation and its treatment and disposal. Medical waste is called as 'infectious materials.' Which waste is generated during the healthcare diagnosis, treatment, immunization, research, testing related to the human beings and animals is known as medical waste.

Medical waste directly effects on sanitation workers, medical and paramedical staff, patients and attenders, public etc. Generally two types of waste are generated by the health facilities. Which is known as risk waste and non risk waste. Medical risk wastes have adverse impacts on human health, animals and environment. Infections waste, pathological waste, sharps waste, pharmaceutical waste, genotoxic waste, chemical waste and radio active waste etc. are known as risk medical waste. Infections medical waste increases the problems of skin disease, tuberculosis etc. Government and non-government have very poor participation in medical waste management. Untreated waste is used in

landfilling, incineration and composting. So such types of medical wastes generate the methane gas which is increased the environmental problems.

Objective of study

The following objectives have been selected to complete the present study–

- 1.To analyse the medical waste generation rate of the study area Meerut city.
- 2.To analyse the medical waste management system of the medical facilities in the study area.
- 3.To analyse the adverse impacts of untreated medical waste on environment and human health.
- 4.To prepare a plan for medical waste management of the study area.

Review of Literature

Many research scholars have completed the research work related to the medical waste generation and its impacts on environment. Medical waste management is a burning issue for the planners, geographers, doctors, economist and engineers. The researcher has made an attempt to arrange the literature related to the research problem. Which is presented as–

Stephen and Elijah (2011) completed their research paper on 'Healthcare waste Management in Nigeria – A Case Study.' They analysed that medical waste management is a serious problem in developing countries. These facilities have poor management of the generated solid waste. They analysed that medical waste constitutes a special category of waste because they contain potentially harmful waste. In their study they found that medical facilities was generated 0.62 kg/person/day and 0.81 kg/bed/day waste in Nigeria. Manar, Sahu and Singh (2014) presented a research paper titled 'Hospital Waste Management in non-teaching Hospitals of Lucknow City, India.' They found that mean hospital waste generation rate 0.56 kg/bed/day in Lucknow city. They found that 50.5% of the hospitals have not biomedical waste department. Only 37.50% hospitals have records about the biomedical waste and segregation. Sharma and Gupta (2017) presented a research paper titled 'Healthcare Waste Management Scenario: A Case Study of Himachal Pradesh, India.' In their study they analysed the compare the healthcare waste generation across private and public hospitals and also analysed the factors responsible for healthcare waste generation. They found that private healthcare facilities are generating more healthcare waste as compared to public hospitals. Rosana, Vincent and Sowmiya (2018) analysed the healthcare waste management in India. Towards a healthier environment. They discussed about the bio-medical waste management and its impact on environment. They discussed the handling and management of healthcare waste is an emerging concern among the sources responsible for generating hazardous waste. Datta, Kaur and Chander (2018) presented a research paper titled 'Biomedical Waste Management in India: Critical Appraisal.' They discussed about the suitable waste management in their paper. They analysed the benefits of the new biomedical waste rules. The pillar of biomedical waste management is segregation of waste at source. They suggested that biomedical waste in red/blue bag or container which for recycling will be sent only to an authorized recycler. They discussed about the difference between in the schedule of 1998 and 2016 for biomedical waste. Aradhya, Savita, Madhu and Narendar (2019) discussed about the awareness and practices of biomedical waste management among healthcare workers. They pointed that these workers mostly effected by the untreated medical waste. In their study they found that knowledge and attitude regarding biomedical waste management among health personal and students of the institute was higher as compare to practice. Ravi and Rampal (2019) analysed the colour coding dustbins are used to depositing the biomedical waste in the hospitals. They discussed about the biomedical waste management rules of 2016 and analysed that the selected hospital Shree Maharaja Gublan Singh is generated 116.37 gram biomedical waste per bed per day. They found that surgical department is generated much biomedical waste than the other department. Husain (2019) discussed about the healthcare waste management in his research paper and found that hazards and infectious waste is very harmful to the environment and the human beings. Infections wastes may contain a variety of pathogenic microorganism. The route of entry into the body for microorganism may be through a puncture, abrasion or cut in the skin, possibly caused by sharps contaminated with pathogens. Vijai, Suryaluxmi and Elayaraja (2023) presented a research paper titled 'A Study on Biomedical Waste Management in India.' They analysed the biomedical waste management challenges. They discussed about the suitable waste disposal method and suggested to save the environmental degradation. Thakur (2024) analysed the biomedical waste management in the context of India and discussed the causes of the medical waste generation. They analysed that the problem of biomedical waste is increasing in urban areas rapidly because the population high birth rate and the slow rate of biomedical treatment.

Methodology

Research Problem

Due to untreated medical waste deposition the problem of environmental degradation is increasing in the study area Meerut city. Medical waste management work is not completing regularly by the health facilities. All medical facilities are depend on the municipal authority to dispose the solid waste. Segaration method is followed here by the few medical facilities. Untreated medical waste are deposited here in open areas.

Study Area

Meerut city is selected to complete the present study. It is the headquarter of Meerut district. In western Uttar Pradesh it is a developed city. It has covered 450 km² geographical area and situated between 28.9845°N latitude and 77.705956 east longitude. It is the second most populous city in the 'National Capital Region.' It is situated 65 km in north from the Delhi. It is developing rapidly due to increasing the population and industrial development. There are present a lot of medical facilities. Some medical facilities have advanced technology and advanced facilities about the treatment in the Meerut city.

Database And Research Methodology

Both types of data has been used in the present study. Primary data has been collected by sampling method from the selected medical facilities. Secondary data related to the medical waste generation, medical facilities, medical waste management and adverse effects of medical waste on environment, human health, animals is collected from the research papers, journals, magazines, Ph.D. thesis, books, websites, hospitals records etc. To collect the primary data the researcher has made a questionnaire and applied it on the sample sites. Medical waste generated amount data has been collected day by day by using the balanced. One month medical waste data has been collected from the selected medical facilities. To find out the result statistical method has been used in this research paper.

Sampling

To complete the present study randomly sampling method has used by the researcher. Selected medical facilities for sample study are given below–

S.No.	Medical Facilities	Selected Units	High Scale	Medium Scale	Low Scale
1.	Hospitals	09	3	3	3
2.	Nursing Homes	09	3	3	3
3.	Clinics	09	3	3	3
4.	Pathology Labs	09	3	3	3
Total		36	12	12	12

Analysis

Medical Waste Generation Sources

All types of health facilities are the big sources of the medical waste generation. Hospitals, nursing home, clinics and pathology labs are the main sources of medical waste. The major sources of the generation of the medical waste are as–

These are the major sources of the medical waste. Medical related other facilities are also the generation sources of the medical waste. Other facilities are as like that blood donation camps, vaccination camps, health checkups camps and vatenary etc.

Generation Of Medical Waste

Medical waste generation has been increasing in the study area Meerut city due to population growth and the improved the medical facilities. Most of the medical waste is not properly treated, separated and disposed of. Due to increasing the medical waste the problem of environmental degradation has been started and effected the human health. Average generation of the medical waste by the health facilities is given below in the table–

Table-1
Per Day Average Generation of the Medical Waste (in kg.) by the Sample Health Facilities in Meerut City (September-2024)

S. No.	Sample Health	Facilities Generation of Solid Waste in kg									Average
		S ₁	S ₂	S ₃	S ₄	S ₅	S ₆	S ₇	S ₈	S ₉	
1.	Hospitals	42.56	38.28	56.25	40.37	32.23	25.78	35.38	51.36	45.24	40.828
2.	Nursing Homes	18.48	22.45	20.78	16.47	21.46	19.35	15.77	25.46	17.35	19.730
3.	Clinics	13.65	11.43	12.56	10.52	14.45	11.84	15.62	9.46	13.86	12.598
4.	Pathology Labs	27.33	30.47	21.45	32.15	19.46	17.52	22.55	25.32	28.14	24.932
Mean (\bar{x})		25.505	25.658	27.760	24.878	21.900	18.622	22.330	27.900	28.148	24.522

Source: Computed by the author on the basis of sample survey.

According to the above table, these selected medical facilities generated rate of solid waste has found 40.828 kg per day in hospitals, 19.730 kg. per day in nursing home, 12.598 kg per day in clinics and 24.932 kg per day in pathology labs in the study area. On the basis of the selected medical facilities generation rate of medical waste has found 1224.84 kg per month in hospitals, 591.9 kg per month in nursing homes, 377.94 kg per month in clinics and 747.96 kg per month in pathology labs. So we can say that health facilities are a big sources of medical waste generation in the study area.

Composition of Medical Waste In The Selected Health Facilities

Medical facilities are generated general waste and hazardous waste. Paper, food, cotton, plastics, glass, clothes, rubber and metals are general medical waste and needles, body fluids, body parts, pharmaceuticals, radioactive materials and cytotoxic drugs etc. are medical hazardous waste. The researcher has made an attempt to analyse the composition of medical waste which has generated by the selected health facilities. The composition of medical waste of the selected health facilities is given below in the table-

Table-2
Composition of the Medical Waste of the Selected Health Facilities in Meerut City (September-2024)

Sr. No.	Sample Health Facilities	Composition of Medical Waste in %							Total
		Plastics	Papers	Glass	Textiles	Metals	Waste Food	Others	
1.	Hospitals	32.60	12.75	5.35	14.20	1.85	16.80	16.45	100
2.	Nursing Homes	30.53	13.48	4.26	17.42	1.30	13.78	19.23	100
3.	Clinics	28.45	11.30	3.18	15.25	1.10	11.47	29.25	100
4.	Pathology Labs	35.50	12.20	7.35	13.32	1.25	8.35	22.03	100
Mean (\bar{x})		31.77	12.43	5.04	15.04	1.38	12.60	21.74	100

Source: Computed by the author on the basis of the sample survey.

According to the above table, the average composition of medical waste have plastics 31.77%, papers 12.43%, glass 5.04%, textiles 15.04%, metals 1.38%, waste food 12.60% and other 21.74% in the study area. A different ratio has been found of the medical waste in the different types of medical facilities here. Pathologies labs have found more generator of the plastics in the selected health facilities. These facilities are generated 35.50% plastics in the medical waste. In the present study we found that according to the health facilities the medical waste is generated in the hospitals. Multi-facilities hospitals are more medical waste generator than the single facilities provider hospitals.

Medical Waste Management In The Study Area

To find out the result related to the technology of the medical waste management the researcher has selected 4 types of medical facilities. During in the observation of the medical waste management we found that very few medical facilities have eco friendly medical waste management in the study area. Mostly health facilities have poor management of the generated waste. These facilities are collected and transported it to the deposit site. Mostly the generated wastes are collected in mixed form, transported and disposed of alongwith municipal solid wastes. The researcher has made an attempt to analyse the medical waste management process of the selected health facilities. Medical waste management of the selected health facilities is given below in the table-

Table-3
Medical Waste Management of the Selected Health Facilities in the Study Area Meerut City (September-2024)

Sr.No.	Health Facilities	Waste Management				
		Collection	Seperation	Transportation	Handover	Disposal
1.	Hospitals	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	No
2.	Nursing Homes	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	No
3.	Clinics	Yes	No	No	Yes	No
4.	Pathology Labs	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	No
Mean (\bar{x})		Yes	Yes	No	Yes	No

Source: Computed by the author on the basis of the sample survey.

According to the above table, we found that all medical facilities are collected the medical waste regularly but they have not disposed and transportation facilities it. During the seperation these medical facilities are used the different types of bins. All medical facilities are handover the waste to the municipality authority for transportation and deposition it. Medical waste is not treated by the medical authority so the problem of medical waste management is increasing in the study area. Due to inadequate infrastructure for waste collection and treatment many problems related to the environment and health issues are increasing in the study area. In the present study the

researcher has found that mostly medical facilities are collected the medical waste in mixed form and handover it to the municipality authority.

Medical Waste Management Level In The Study Area

To analyse the medical waste management level of the selected medical facilities the researcher has made an attempt to find out the result on the basis of the rating which has provided on the basis of scientific method of medical waste management. The selected medical facilities and their waste management rating is given below in the table-

Table-4
Rating of the Selected Medical Facilities in Medical Waste Management in the Study Area (September-2024)

S. No.	Health Facilities	Rating of the Selected Health Facilities (0-10)									Average
		S ₁	S ₂	S ₃	S ₄	S ₅	S ₆	S ₇	S ₈	S ₉	
1.	Hospitals	6	8	5	7	6	5	8	6	6	6.33
2.	Nursing Homes	5	7	6	8	7	7	6	8	7	6.78
3.	Clinics	6	5	5	6	6	7	5	5	6	5.67
4.	Pathology Labs	7	6	8	7	7	7	8	8	8	7.33
Mean (x̄)		6.00	6.50	5.50	7.00	6.50	6.50	6.75	6.75	6.75	6.53

Source: Computed by the author on the basis of the sample survey.

According to the above table, the rating of selected health facilities in biomedical waste management has found 6.53 in the study area. It is indicated average medical waste management systems in the study area. The rating of hospitals in medical waste management has found 6.33 and 6.78 rating has found in nursing homes, 5.67 rating in clinics and 7.33 rating has found in pathology labs about the medical waste management. So on the basis of the above mentioned data the pathology labs have high rating in medical waste management than the other medical facilities in the study area.

Health Facilities In Meerut City

In the present study the researcher has made an attempt to analyse the health facilities and the dependency of the population in Meerut city. Health facilities and population dependency is given below in the table-

Table-5
Health Facilities and Population Dependency in Meerut City (2023)

S.No.	Types of Health Facilities	Units	Population Dependency (Per Unit)
1.	Allopathic Hospitals	257	5079
2.	Primary Health Centers	10	130543
3.	Aayurvedic Hospitals	02	652715
4.	Unani Hospital	01	1305429
5.	Homeopathic Hospitals	02	652715
6.	Family and Maternity Centers	08	163179

Source: District Statistical Magazine, Meerut District, Year 2023

According to the above table, we found that the population dependency is very high on the health facilities in the study area. Total population of the Meerut city has found 1305429 census 2011. In the present study we found that there are present 257 allopathic hospitals, 10 primary health centers, 02 aayurvedic hospitals, 01 unani hospital, 02 homeopathic hospitals and 08 family and maternity welfare centers in the Meerut city.

Impact of Medical Waste on Environment.

Untreated medical waste has a huge environmental issue. According to the report by the world health organisation the medical waste accumulated during the pandemic increased plastics pollution in the ocean by 10 times. The untreated biomedical waste may cause negative impact on the water quality as different pollutants may each out from the waste dumping sites into the general water. Improper disposal of medical waste containing, pathogens like bacteria, viruses and parasites can lead to the spread of infections diseases if they come into contact with humans and animals though contaminated soil and water. Air, water, and soil are polluted by the untreated medical waste and effected the human health. Virus and infections diseases are the result of the lack of facilities of the medical disposal. Malaria, dengue fever, respiratory diseases, skin diseases etc. are the result of the untreated medical waste deposition incineration is a method of medical waste disposal. This method can release harmful pollutants into the air and create the problem of respiratory systems.

Medical waste contains heavy metals, including cadmium, lead and mercury, which can be taken up by plants and introduced into the food chain. The availability of nitrates and phosphates in landfill leachates is considered as contamination. Incineration of biomedical waste can contribute to acid rain and spread of diseases. Untreated medical waste is very harmful to the health workers, patients and waste collectors.

Conclusion

In the present study the researcher has found that untreated medical waste is increasing in the study area and increased the problems of environmental degradation. Medical waste disposal sites have high level of air, water and soil pollution. Landfilling method of medical waste is not suitable for the environment. Infection, diseases are the result of the untreated medical waste deposition with the municipal waste. Health workers and medical waste collectors has found highly effected by the medical waste. After Covid-19 the medical waste is generating in high amount in the healthcare facilities in the study area due to adopt the sanitisation in cleaners in health services. Medical waste is collected properly in the health facilities but it is not treated properly. So the problems of environmental degradation and health issues are increasing day by day.

Suggestions for the future Study

Untreated medical waste created many problems in the study area, so we need a suitable plan for medical waste management to reduce its impact on environment and human health. The researcher has made some suggestions for biomedical waste management.

Which are as followings–

1. Collection of the medical waste should be properly every day by the authority and the agency.
2. To control the infectious diseases by the medical waste we should segregated the waste on the generated sources.
3. Suitable disposal method should be used in disposed the medical waste.
4. Covered vehicles should be used during in transportation of the medical waste.
5. Proper kit should be provided to the health workers and waste collectors in the hospitals to control the infectious diseases and viral diseases.
6. Stored the collected medical waste in a safe place in the healthcare facilities campus not beyond 48 hours.
7. Biomedical waste management rules should be followed to the medical facilities to reduce the level of medical waste.
8. Colour coding for biomedical waste management in hospitals to segregate the waste should be compulsory.
9. Awareness programmes should be presented by the government, NGO's and medical authority about the impact of biomedical waste on environment and health
10. in every month.
11. Medical waste disposal sites should be established outside from the residential area to present the viral and infections diseases.

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